

STATUS REPORT 2022-10-31

GGOS Focus Area Unified Height System (FA-UHS)

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Present Status and Progress

The GGOS Focus Area “Unified Height System” (GGOS-FA-UHS, formerly Theme 1) was established at the 2010 GGOS Planning Meeting (February 1 - 3, Miami, Florida, USA) to lead and coordinate the efforts required for the establishment of a global unified height system that serves as a basis for the standardisation of height systems worldwide. Starting point was the results delivered by the IAG Inter-Commission Project 1.2 Vertical Reference Frames (IAG-ICP1.2-VRF), which was operative from 2003 to 2011. During the 2011-2015 term, different discussions focussed on the best possible definition of a global unified vertical reference system resulted in the IAG resolution for the Definition and realisation of an International Height Reference System (IHRF) that was approved during the 2015 General Assembly of the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG) in Prague, Czech Republic. In the term 2015-2019, actions dedicated to investigate the best strategy for the realisation of the IHRF (i.e., the establishment of the International Height Reference Frame – IHRF) were undertaken. In particular, a preliminary station selection for the IHRF reference network was achieved and different computation procedures for the determination of potential values as IHRF coordinates were evaluated.

At present, we are preparing a special issue on Reference Systems in Physical Geodesy to be published in the Journal of Geodesy. This special issue includes the scientific description of the best available strategies for the geoid modelling as well as key contributions for the establishment of the IHRF/IHRF and the ITRF/ITRF (International Terrestrial Gravity Reference System and Frame). Paper submission started in October 2019 and was closed in May 2020. We received 22 manuscripts; 19 of them are already published, and one is being revised by the authors.

Sánchez et al. (2021), present an extensive guideline for the realisation of the IHRF, including:

- Strategy for the appropriate handling of permanent tide effects in the determination of IHRF coordinates in the mean-tide system
- Strategy for the determination and evaluation of IHRF coordinates depending on the data availability (specially surface gravity data and topography models)
- Strategy to improve the input data required for the determination of IHRF coordinates
- Strategy for the IHRF station selection in regional and national densifications
- Strategy to ensure the usability and long-term sustainability of the IHRF

Based on this publication, a current international action with the contribution of more than 50 colleagues concentrates on the computation of IHRF coordinates at the reference stations selected initially for the IHRF reference frame. The IHRF core network comprises about 170 stations,

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presently, IHRF coordinates have been computed for 55% of these stations, 21% are being in evaluation and 24% are still open (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. IHRF reference network: red dots represent stations with IHRF coordinates determined, blue dots represent stations with IHRF coordinate determination in process, and green dots represent IHRF stations to be determined in the near future.

Planned Actions and Milestones

The planned activities of the FA-UHS may be summarised as follows:

- (1) To complete the first IHRF solution to be presented at the IUGG2023 General Assembly in Berlin, Germany;
- (2) To continue refining standards, conventions, and guidelines to support a consistent determination of the IHRF at regional and national levels;
- (3) With the support of the IAG Commission 2, the International Gravity Field Service (IGFS) and the Inter-Commission Committee on Theory (ICCT) to promote the study of quality assessment in the determination of potential values and determination of potential changes with time. In this way, following working/study groups play a main role to achieve the GGOS-GA-UHS objectives:
 - IAG Commission 2 working group *Error assessment of the 1-cm geoid experiment*, chaired by T Jiang (China) and VN Grigoriadis (Greece).
 - IAG ICCT study group *Geoid/quasi-geoid modelling for realisation of the geopotential height datum*, chaired by J Huang (Canada) and YM Wang (USA).

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- GGOS-FA-UHS and IGFS working group *Implementation of the International Height Reference Frame (IHRF)*, chaired by L Sánchez (Germany) and R Barzaghi (Italy).
- (4) In agreement with the IGFS and the IAG Commission 2, to design a strategy to install an operational infrastructure within the IGFS to ensure the maintenance and availability of the IHRF in a long-term basis. A proposal in this regard will be presented to the IAG Executive Committee also at IUGG2023.

References

Sánchez L., Ågren J., Huang J., Wang Y.M., Mäkinen J., Pail R., Barzaghi R., Vergos G.S., Ahlgren K., Liu Q.: *Strategy for the realisation of the International Height Reference System (IHRF)*. Journal of Geodesy, 95(3), 10.1007/s00190-021-01481-0, 2021